

Exploring the Hidden World Beneath Our Waves:

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What Decades of Ocean Observations Reveal About California's Changing Ocean

A living, changing ocean

The ocean is the closest thing we have to an alien world, home to glowing, drifting, often unearthly-looking life forms that shape the ecosystems we depend on. But while the ocean may feel like another planet, it's actually very much part of our own planet, and it plays a huge role in our daily lives. For example, the ocean helps regulate the climate, absorbs carbon dioxide from the air and helps drive the global economy with contributions from fisheries, recreation and scientific research. From the depths of the sea, where gelatinous creatures use special senses to find food, to the California sea lions feasting on anchovies along the coast, to the microscopic plants and animals that form the base of the food web, the ocean is home to all kinds of fascinating creatures. Over the past 100 years, however, the ocean

has undergone significant changes that have put the health of both marine organisms and humans at risk. For over 75 years, the California Cooperative Oceanic Fisheries Investigations, known as CalCOFI, has studied this hidden world, offering one of the clearest long-term records we have of ocean change.

The birth and evolution of CalCOFI

In the 1930s, California's coast was famous for sardines. They were caught in the millions and became one of the biggest fisheries on the West Coast. Scientists warned that the catch was getting too high, but the fishing continued, and by the 1950s, the sardines had almost completely disappeared. No one knew if the collapse was caused by overfishing, changing ocean conditions, or something else entirely.

CalCOFI was formed in 1949 to study the cause of this population collapse. But as researchers collected data, they realized that to understand the mystery of what happened to one species, they needed to understand the whole ocean ecosystem around it. Today, the focus of these cruises has shifted to a more holistic approach, studying the California coast marine ecosystem how we manage marine resources, while monitoring both climate change impacts and natural oceanic variability, such as El Niño. The team goes to sea four times a year to collect some of the most crucial information to understand the marine environment and our changing ocean, including pH, dissolved oxygen, temperature, phytoplankton, zooplankton, marine mammal and bird observations.

What started as a search for answers about sardines has become one of the world's longest-running marine programs and a powerful long-term record of how the California Current, and our changing ocean, works.

What CalCOFI measures and why it matters

CalCOFI cruises take a suite of measurements to understand ocean conditions. Temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen and salinity are some of the abiotic (non-living) measurements that help researchers determine present-day ocean conditions and track how things have changed over time. Phytoplankton and zooplankton, microscopic plants and animals are also collected using very fine-meshed nets at various angles and depths to tell us what kind of communities live in different layers of the ocean. But why do researchers care about these microscopic organisms? Plankton tell us what's happening at the base of the food web and can indicate the health of ocean ecosystems. In addition, net tows collect fish eggs and larvae for researchers to help them understand fish communities and make fishery stock assessments. Researchers aboard these cruises also observe and count seabirds and marine mammals, such as brown pelicans and humpback whales.

Retrieving a CalBOBL (Bongo) net. Photo credit: Angela Klemmedson

Long-term monitoring data such as those collected by CalCOFI are incredibly important for a variety of reasons. The temperature measurements can help detect marine heatwaves and track natural oceanic and climatic cycles such as El Niño. Chlorophyll and phytoplankton measurements can help predict algal blooms and reveal how they have changed over time as climate conditions shift.

From plankton to predators: Life in the California Current

To understand what CalCOFI's data tell us about the marine ecosystem, it helps to start small. Phytoplankton and zooplankton form the base of the food web, converting sunlight and nutrients into energy that supports nearly all ocean life. Small fish feed on these plankton, larger fish feed on smaller fish and top predators such as sharks, seabirds and marine mammals

depend on these larger prey. In this way, energy moves upward through the food web, linking microscopic organisms to the largest animals in the ocean. So, what happens at the base of the food web is incredibly important for the organisms that feed on them.

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Diatoms, a type of microscopic algae that drift through the ocean, are one example of phytoplankton. Diatoms have glass-like shells and, just like terrestrial plants, turn sunlight into energy through photosynthesis. They breathe in carbon dioxide and breathe out oxygen, making them important to the ocean's dissolved oxygen levels. Dinoflagellates are another type of phytoplankton. They are essential food for tiny fish, but some species can cause harmful algal blooms such as red tides that are common in Southern California. Algal blooms caused by dinoflagellates can lead to high levels of toxins (e.g., brevetoxins, saxitoxin, domoic acid) in fish and shellfish that can be harmful to humans and some marine life. CalCOFI monitors phytoplankton communities, which can provide insight into harmful algal blooms and helps fishermen and shellfish harvesters determine if the organisms they are catching are safe to eat. This is one of the many ways that CalCOFI data helps keep both the California marine ecosystem and people safe.

Moving up a level, we arrive at zooplankton, which are the tiny drifters that also fuel the food web. Some zooplankton species commonly found along the California coast are animals such as copepods (e.g. *Calanus pacificus* or

Acartia tonsa) and krill (e.g. *Euphausia pacifica* or *Thysanoessa spinifera*). Copepods are a crucial food source for a variety of animals, from anchovies to seabirds. Krill are similar to shrimp and make up a large portion of whale diets. Because zooplankton fuel the marine food web, changes in their population in the California Current can signal potential impacts on the organisms that rely on them for food.

Some of the most important animals studied by CalCOFI are not the largest or the rarest, but the ones that connect plankton to the rest of the food web. Anchovies and sardines are small schooling fish known as forage fish because they are a primary food source for seabirds, marine mammals and larger fish. Sardines are especially important to CalCOFI's history because the collapse of California's sardine fishery in the mid-20th century was one of the key reasons the program was created. Squid are another group of mid-sized marine organisms in this food web. They migrate vertically, spending hours during the day in deeper water and moving closer to the surface at night, where some species can produce bioluminescent flashes. Larger fish, such as Pacific mackerel and California halibut, depend on these smaller animals for food. All of these species rely, directly or indirectly, on healthy plankton populations, showing how energy moves upward through the ecosystem.

CalCOFI cruises regularly observe some of the largest animals on Earth, including blue whales, gray whales and humpback whales. Blue whales are the largest animals ever known to exist and feed almost entirely on krill, consuming several tons per day during feeding season. Gray whales are famous for their long migration from Arctic feeding grounds to breeding lagoons in Baja California, passing through CalCOFI survey waters along the way. Humpback whales are known for breaching and complex songs and are often seen feeding where anchovies are abundant. California sea lions are

equally common; these social and vocal predators are frequently spotted resting on buoys during surveys. These animals depend on dense prey patches that form only when plankton communities are productive, making them visible indicators of ecosystem health.

Masked booby flying over the ocean. Photo credit: Tammy Russell

Seabirds are another key group monitored during CalCOFI cruises because they respond quickly to changes in ocean conditions. Brown pelicans are often seen diving headfirst into the water to catch fish and are a conservation success story after population declines linked to pesticide use. Black-footed albatrosses are long-distance travelers that spend much of their lives out in the open ocean. Conversely, the small ashy storm-petrel is an endemic species (a species that occurs naturally in the California Current geographic region and is not found anywhere else on the planet) that nests

on offshore islands. Brandt's cormorants are skilled underwater hunters that rely on nearshore fish. Scientists record bird sightings during surveys to track shifts in species distribution and abundance. Because seabirds depend on predictable food sources, changes in their presence can signal changes in ocean productivity. Some surprising observations recently included masked boobies and waved albatrosses, species often found in the Galápagos Islands.

Occasionally, CalCOFI surveys document apex predators such as great white sharks and orcas. These animals sit at the top of the food web and rely on a chain of prey that begins with plankton, continues through fish and squid and extends to marine mammals. Although they are seen less frequently, their presence reflects the overall structure of the ecosystem. CalCOFI's long-term datasets allow scientists to examine whether these food webs remain stable or are shifting over time. By studying everything from microscopic plankton to apex predators, CalCOFI provides a complete picture of how the California Current ecosystem functions and changes.

Underwater shot of a CTD-Rosette during calm conditions. A CTD is a device used for water sampling in deep water and is made up of several small probes attached to a large wheel. CTD stands for “Conductivity, Temperature, Depth”. Photo credit: James Wilkinson

Who uses CalCOFI data?

You might be wondering who uses all of this data, and how is it used? State and federal agencies, as well as several research institutions, rely on CalCOFI data to guide their decisions. These agencies and organizations work together to ensure that California’s marine resources and ecosystems are safeguarded. One way CalCOFI data help is to assess water quality. For example, the California State Water Resources Control Board (State Water Board) uses pH, dissolved inorganic carbon and dissolved oxygen data collected by CalCOFI to understand ocean chemistry conditions along the California coast and ensure that appropriate water quality standards are

being met. CalCOFI data are also used to inform fisheries management and ecosystem assessments; scientists at NOAA Fisheries analyze long-term records of ocean temperature, nutrients and larval fish abundance to track changes in commercially and ecologically important species, while the California Department of Fish and Wildlife uses these data to better understand how fish populations replenish themselves, supporting science-based decisions that promote sustainable fisheries along the California coast.

Seeing the patterns: 75 years of ocean change

Understanding the ocean requires more than short snapshots of data, it requires time. With more than 75 years of observations, CalCOFI allows scientists to see patterns that would otherwise remain hidden. Long-term data reveal how climate-driven changes affect the California Current, including warming trends, ocean acidification and hypoxia, shifts in ocean currents and major marine heatwaves such as the event known as the “Blob.” These records also show how species distributions change over time, as plankton, fish, birds and mammals respond to new conditions. CalCOFI provides the whole story, showing how the ocean we see today reflects decades of change.

The ocean studied by CalCOFI is not a distant or unfamiliar place. Rather it is part of our own backyard, shaping California’s coast and the life it supports. By tracking how the ecosystem shifts over time, CalCOFI helps explain why those changes matter to people and wildlife alike. The message is simple: the ocean is still full of surprises, and long-term research is one of the best tools we have to uncover them.

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